

Synthesis of Possible Antiparkinsonian Compounds. Part X Synthesis of 2,6,8 Trisubstituted Benzoxazinones and their Corresponding 3-Hydroxy-quinazolinones

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Some new benzoxazinones and quinazolinones have been synthesised with a view to testing their anti-parkinsonism activity.

QUINAZOLINONES have been reported to exhibit pronounced central nervous system depressant¹⁻³, anti-convulsant^{4,5} and musculerelaxant^{6,7} properties. Since parkinsonism is a chronic malady of the central nervous system and most of the synthetic drugs which are recommended in this therapy are either antihistaminics or anticholinergics⁸, authors, therefore, were prompted to synthesise newer quinazolinones to study their pharmacological effects.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route :

X = H-; Br-.
R = C₆H₅CONHCH₂-; C₆H₅CH(OH)-;
C₆H₅CH = CH-; 2OH(3 : 5 Br)-; C₆H₂-.

3 : 5-Dibromo-anthranilic acid(I) :

This was obtained following the procedure of Rosanoff *et al*⁹.

Substituted benzoxazinones(II) :

A mixture of anthranilic acid or 3 : 5 dibromo-anthranilic acid (0.01 mole) and acid-chloride (0.02 mole) (viz., hippuroyl-chloride, mandeloyl-chloride, styryl-chloride and 3 : 5-dibromo-salicyloyl-chloride) in 30 ml. of anhydrous pyridine was stirred by cooling for one hour. The reaction mixture was

then further stirred for one hour at room temperature. A pasty mass obtained which was washed thoroughly with sodium-bicarbonate solution (5%) to remove any unreacted acid. A solid separated out which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from appropriate solvent. Various benzoxazinones thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

3-Hydroxy-quinazolinones (III) :

A mixture of hydroxylamine-hydrochloride (0.002 mole) and benzoxazinone (0.002 mole) in 30 ml. of anhydrous pyridine was heated under reflux under hydrous conditions for 6 hr. The resulting mixture was then poured on into the crushed ice containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 ml.). The yellow solid which separated out, was filtered off, dried and recrystallised from any polar solvent. The quinazolinones thus synthesised are listed in Table 2.

Pharmacology :

Two compounds were subjected for their toxicity test (determination of ALD 50 values) and anti-tremorine activity.

Toxicity test¹⁰ :

All the compounds were well tolerated upto the doses of 400 mg/kg without any toxic manifestations. This observation indicated the non-toxicity of these benzoxazinones and quinazolinones.

Anti-tremor effect :

For anti-tremor activity, the albino-mice of either sex were chosen. The compound under investigation was administered intraperitoneally. One hour after the drug administration, tremorinehydrochloride (solution in distilled water) was injected to the mice (5 mg/kg). The mice were then observed for the occurrence of tremor. None of the compounds was found to possess significant anti-tremorine activity.

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TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTED BENZOXAZINONES

Sl No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CONHCH ₂ -	160°	C ₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	10.00	9.69
2.	Br	C ₆ H ₅ CONHCH ₂ -	100-101	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	6.39	6.51
3.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CHOH-	71-73	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₃	5.53	5.42
4.	Br	C ₆ H ₅ CHOH-	160	C ₁₅ H ₉ NO ₃ Br ₂	3.40	3.21
5.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH-	147-148	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ NO ₂	5.62	5.38
6.	Br	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH-	85-86	C ₁₆ H ₉ NO ₂ Br ₂	3.43	3.29
7.	H	2-OH(3 : 5-Br).C ₆ H ₂ -	75-76	C ₁₄ H ₇ NO ₃ Br ₂	3.52	3.43
8.	Br	2-OH(3 : 5-Br).C ₆ H ₂ -	250	C ₁₄ H ₅ NO ₃ Br ₄	2.52	2.38

Note :—All the benzoxazinones were recrystallised from methanol. The percent yield ranged from 50-65.

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED-3-HYDROXY-QUINAZOLINONES

Sl. No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis Nitrogen	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CONHCH ₂	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	14.23	14.21
2.	Br	C ₆ H ₅ CONHCH ₂	88-89	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ Br ₂	9.27	9.08
3.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CHOH	88-89	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	10.44	10.62
4.	Br	C ₆ H ₅ CHOH	166-167	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	6.57	6.18
5.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH	108-109	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.64	10.25
6.	Br	C ₆ H ₅ CH = CH	107-108	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂	6.63	6.28
7.	H	3 : 5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl.	92-93	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	6.79	6.45
8.	Br	3 : 5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl.	225-226	C ₁₄ H ₆ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₄	4.91	4.85

Note :—Solvent used for the recrystallisation was ethanol. The percent yield ranged from 45-50.

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